

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND ECOLOGICAL POLICY OF THE STATE

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ABSTRACT

In order to ensure the sustainable development of the economy, it is necessary to approach the social, economic and environmental aspects equally and implement their development in a balanced manner. World experience has proven the efficiency of the model of sustainable development of national economies of states that combines economic, social and environmental priorities. The transition to a new development model called the sustainable development model was a natural reaction of the world community striving to preserve its existence and further development. The article presents the role of socio-economic aspects in ensuring sustainable development and the results of the research conducted to determine the main directions of environmental policy in accordance with the requirements of the modern era.

Keywords: sustainable development, society, socio-economic development, ecological environment, environmental policy.

Introduction

The actuality of the subject. The ecological development strategy implemented in the Republic of Azerbaijan and the protection of the environment in this area are aimed at ensuring the sustainable and balanced development of the country. In particular, it creates a competitive environment based on the principles of sustainable development, social welfare that meets high standards, the efficient use of natural resources and the formation of an ecological security system that ensures reliable protection of the population.

While human well-being is closely related to the environment formed in the society in which he lives, the development of the society depends on the economic, social and environmental opportunities surrounding it. However, the limitation of natural resources, globalization, population growth, environmental pollution, global warming, erosion, landslides, natural disasters, etc. such problems put the sustainability of the existing ecosystem at risk and limit the development of future generations. It is not enough to develop ecosystem and human development management programs to prevent this process. In this regard, a number of scientific approaches, models and concepts have been put forward to study, measure and evaluate sustainable development as a problem in the global and regional as well as national framework. [1]

In 1992, the concept of sustainable development was adopted in Rio de Janeiro with the initiative of the UN and the participation of 172 heads of state. The development program of the concept defines three aspects of sustainable development: economic growth, social development and environmental security. Sustainable development is a new paradigm that combines economic, ecological and social components in the selection and realization of the development indicators of humanity, reflecting the understanding of the vital im-

portance of a systematic approach.[5] In general, sustainable development is based on two important factors that are closely related to each other, which means that the concepts of "sustainable development" and "sustainable economic development" are not so different. One of these factors is the demand factor, which is more important and necessary for the existence of the poor segment of the population. The second factor, called limitation, is mainly determined by the state of technology and the organization of society, but it is also related to the ability of the environment to meet the needs of present and future generations. As it can be seen, the main task of sustainable development is expressed by continuous (continuous) satisfaction of the needs and desires of the society. [2,s.364]

Although social, economic and environmental aspects are also recognized to be important, which aspect is necessarily more important is a controversial topic.

Until the Brundtland Commission in 1987 defined approaches to social, economic and environmental aspects, they were considered to be mutually developing concepts. After the Brundtland Commission report, two different approaches emerged regarding the question of how the mentioned aspects are related to each other:

1. According to the first approach, economic aspects are decided within social aspects, and social aspects are decided within environmental aspects. If we consider this approach as three overlapping circles, the economic aspects will be the innermost, the environmental aspects will be the outermost, and the social aspects will be in the middle. This approach is also called "Matryoshka model". In this approach, the innermost location of economic aspects is not related to its playing a main role. In this approach, it is emphasized that the economic aspects are the social aspects surrounding it, and the social aspects are part of the issues related to the environment. In this way, it is tried to show that all three aspects are related without separating one from

the other. According to the result of this approach, although the economic and social aspects are related to each other, the aspects related to the environment can continue to exist without depending on the others because they are of the most general nature [3].

2. According to the second approach, one of the three aspects related to sustainable development is independent of the other, and the part where all three of them are connected and intersect is the state of sustainability. This concept is also called the "Three Pillar Model". This pattern can also be described as an intersecting triple circle. Each of these circles covers an aspect, economic, social and environmental aspects. In the part where all three aspects intersect, stable development is ensured in their connection with each other. In contrast to the first approach, in this approach, all three aspects are equally important, and the case where one of the aspects does not intersect is characterized as a case of "weak stability". The situation in which all three aspects are equally represented and their balanced development is ensured is characterized as "strong stability" [4].

Summarizing the experience of socio-economic development of the advanced countries of the world proves that it is possible to achieve great success only when conditions are created for the full formation and optimal application of the life forces of each specific person, when his individual qualities are highly valued. In the socio-economic field, the essential forces of personality mean the potential and actual ability of a person to reproduce his life with the individual and social means applied here. In this case, socio-economic relations include the system of relations between people in the spheres of production, distribution, exchange and consumption.

One of the main directions of the sustainable development strategy and the most priority is to ensure the ecological safety of the environment, to improve and restore the ecological situation and balance. Because a sustainable ecological situation is considered the most leading and pioneering indicator of ensuring sustainable human development [6, c.203]

Materials and methods

Analysis, synthesis, logical judgment, comparative analysis and deduction methods were used to comprehensively and deeply study the solution of these issues in the ecological field of national economy development. The information base of the research is made up of the official data of the State Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the State Statistics Committee, local and foreign academic publications and reports.

One of the first international initiatives to take decisive steps towards turning the planet into a healthy and safe place under the general partnership of countries was put forward at the "Millennium Summit" held in New York, USA in September 2000. Thus, at the Summit, the Millennium Declaration was adopted, in which eight global Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were established to create a general framework for creating significant positive changes in the lives of people around the world for the period up to 2015. These MDGs included goals such as eliminating

extreme poverty and hunger, achieving universal primary education, gender equality and women's empowerment, reducing child mortality, strengthening women's health, preventing infectious diseases, and ensuring environmental safety.[7]

The state of Azerbaijan has adopted a national program for ecologically sustainable socio-economic development since 2003. The Republic of Azerbaijan signed the Paris Agreement, which is an addition to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, on April 22, 2016 and ratified it in October of the same year. The Paris Agreement is an agreement that regulates measures to reduce carbon dioxide in the atmosphere from 2020 according to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. The agreement was developed during the Paris Climate Conference instead of the Kyoto Protocol, adopted by consensus on December 12, 2015, and April 22, 2016. was signed in 2008. According to this agreement, the Republic of Azerbaijan, as its contribution to initiatives to mitigate the effects of global climate change, has set a goal of maintaining a 35% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 compared to the base year, i.e. 1990. [8]

The purpose of the research is to develop the economic methods and mechanisms of the sustainable development of the economic-ecological system of Azerbaijan.

Carrying out large-scale work in the direction of solving environmental problems in Azerbaijan, the state policy aimed at improving the environmental situation is an important component of the country's long-term development strategy.

The main essence of the environmental policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan is to protect ecosystems in order to ensure that people live in an ecologically clean environment, to ensure sustainable development with the efficient use of natural resources, minimal harmful impact on the environment, restoration and protection of its original state.

In the direction of environmental protection and efficient use of natural resources, "Socio-economic development strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2022-2026", "Transformation of our world: Agenda in the field of sustainable development until 2030", "Social strategy of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2019-2023" - economic development State Program", "Measure Plan for 2020-2022 on ensuring efficient use of water resources", "State Program for 2020-2024 on geological study of the subsoil and efficient use of mineral-raw material base" and actions are carried out within the framework of other programs.

In order to organize the solid household waste management system across the country in accordance with modern standards and to create the relevant infrastructure, by the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated November 27, 2021, "Commission on the management of solid household waste throughout the country, including territories freed from occupation" was created.

A lot of work has been done in the field of waste management in the Republic of Azerbaijan in recent years. According to the annual report of the State Statistics Committee, a total of 3984.1 thousand tons of

waste was generated in the country in 2022, or 5.4 percent more than the previous year, and 66.7 percent of them were solid household waste, and 33.3 percent were the production activities of enterprises. created different types of wastes. 78.3 percent of the 2658.3 thousand tons of solid household waste generated last year were transported to landfills for disposal, 21.2 percent were used for energy production, and 0.5 percent were sold within the country. 205.3 million kWh or 6.3 percent more electricity than in 2021 was produced due to the use of household waste.

Last year, 28.5 percent of industrial waste was used as raw material in enterprises, 42.7 percent was sold domestically, 3.8 percent was exported, 13.8 percent was transported to landfills for disposal, including residues generated in industry and other areas of the economy. 11.2 percent remained in enterprises. As a result of the production activities of enterprises, 337.1 thousand tons of hazardous waste were generated in 2022, and their share in the total amount of waste was 8.5 percent. 63.1 percent of the waste was generated in the mining industry enterprises, most of which fall on the share of the enterprises located in Baku city. Last year, 55,000 tons of hazardous waste were completely neutralized, including residues from previous years.[9]

The result

Effective use of water resources in the direction of creating a clean ecological environment, protection of the ecological environment of the Caspian Sea, waste management, reduction of the negative effects of climate change, modernization of observation and monitoring systems, protection of atmospheric air, protection of biodiversity, development of ecotourism and aquaculture, protection of forest cover, greenery and increasing, rehabilitating polluted areas, increasing the fertility of soil resources, expanding the mineral-raw material base and efficient use of natural resources, increasing ecological thinking are the main priority directions.

The main goal of the environmental policy implemented in the Republic of Azerbaijan is to ensure sustainable development with the protection of existing ecological systems, economic potential and efficient use of natural resources in order to meet the needs of current and future generations. In order to ensure sustainable development from an ecological point of view, it is necessary to eliminate serious environmental problems that arise during economic activity, and to minimize their negative impact on the environment.

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